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INSTITUTUL PENTRU STUDII POLITICE DE APĂRARE ȘI ISTORIE MILITARĂ

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Consequences on European defence integration entailed by the establishment of the European Intervention Initiative

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ABSTRACT

European Intervention Initiative (EI2) was put forward by Emmanuel Macron in 2017 for enhancing the process of European integration in the field of defence. The proposal took off and eventually attracted 13 member states and facilitated the deployment of two operations outside Europe. Representing a form of differentiated defence integration carried out outside the framework of the European Union (EU) but involving mainly EU members it was opened to the criticism that it runs the risk of affecting the Common Security and Defence Policy which, back in 2017, was in full process of consolidation. The examination of this concern, voiced by politicians and scholars, informs the article which approaches it at the level of both the main objective and the concrete outcomes of the EI2. It is concluded that there is a problematic complementarity between EU and EI2 and, based on its underlining rationales, a possible approach to improving it is suggested.

Keywords: European Intervention Initiative, Common Security and Defence Policy, Permanent Structured Cooperation, differentiated European defence integration, European Union, France.

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Introduction

Differentiated integration at the level of the European Union (EU), when considered internally, refers to the lack of uniformity with respect to participation of member states in specific policies developed therein or, in other words, the possibility of member states to advance towards integration at different paces¹. One EU policy where internal differentiation is strongly present is the Common Security and Defence Policy (CSDP)², where it gives raise to what is usually called differentiated defence integration³. External differentiation describes the participation of non-EU countries to certain EU policies which are designed

to provide this option⁴ and CSDP illustrates this form of differentiation by enabling states that are not members of the EU to take part, for example, in the Permanent Structured Cooperation (PESCO) and in missions and operations⁵. However, differentiated defence integration also develops outside the framework of European Union and, when it brings together both EU and non-EU countries, it becomes another dimension of external differentiation⁶; the Framework Nations Concept (FNC), the Joint Expeditionary Force (JEF) and the European Intervention Initiative (EI2) are all illustrative for this approach to enhance at sub-regional level the integration in the area of defence⁷.

Differentiated integration generates support among experts who underline its potential to accommodate in the process of European integration the heterogeneity among the growing number of EU members; it is argued that more advanced states on the path of integration would generate a centripetal force which will eventually bring all the others in⁸. Critics of differentiated integration point out that it operates as an incentive for disunity, because it introduces dividing lines that are detrimental to the prospects of the EU⁹. In the peculiar case of EI2, various members of the European Union, including Germany, voiced concerns about the potential damaging effects that it could entail for the enhancement of ESDP, particularly for the then newly created PESCO¹⁰. Their attitude was fuelled by the fact that EI2 was proposed, while final arrangements for PESCO, whose ultimate design did not satisfy France, were ongoing¹¹. There was also the concern that EI2 could undermine the EU Battlegroups by operating as their competitor¹². The absence of any formal connection between EI2 and the EU and the doubts about their complementarity were the main reasons for which some prospective countries delayed their EI2 membership¹³. At a higher theoretical level, it is maintained that the EI2 actually calls into question the effectiveness of EU in advancing European defence integration¹⁴.

Implications for ESDP are, thus, a central topic in the political and academic consideration of EI2 and this article aims at examining concerns about the compatibility between EI2 and ESDP. To this purpose, the first section refers to the origins of EI2, as well as to its design, membership and operational outcomes, while the assessment of the EI2-ESDP interplay is addressed in its second section.

European Intervention Initiative— an overview of its inception and implementation

The idea of establishing EI2 was launched in 2017 by the President of France, Emmanuel Macron, as part of his landmark speech about

Europe delivered at Sorbonne University¹⁵. Macron approached this topic within the context of his reflections on providing Europe with capabilities for operating autonomously, considering that EI2 complemented the progress already made by means of PESCO and the European Defence Fund. According to Macron, the added value of EI2 laid in building a common strategic culture across Europe whose absence was a significant factor impeding the development of a substantial defence cooperation among European states. The French president conceived this initiative as a long-term process, taking as its starting point the hosting by French Armed Forces of military personnel from all interested European countries and aiming at enabling working together within the fields of intelligence, planning, support and operational anticipation.

Macron's initiative reflected his conviction that defence policy provided France with an opportunity to enhance its international stance, an objective whose pursuit characterised French foreign policy since Charles de Gaulle¹⁶. EI2 was conceived almost exclusively by Emmanuel Macron, who did not rely on the expertise from the French ministries with responsibilities in the areas of foreign and European affairs and in that of defence¹⁷. Macron was motivated to put forward the EI2 initiative by his dissatisfaction with the support that France received from European countries in fighting threats coming from its southern neighbourhood (Sahel, sub-Saharan Africa), an attitude that, in his view, resulted from divergent threat perceptions¹⁸. The proposal also reflected the difficulties experienced by the French armed forces, which were exposed to a severe overstretching because of their involvement in several operations, closed or ongoing at the time of Sorbonne speech, conducted in Africa and the Middle East: Operation Serval, Operation Barkhane, Operation Chammal, Operation Sangaris¹⁹. Moreover, Macron was deeply dissatisfied by what he considered as the low effectiveness of the European Union, with respect to conducting on short notice crisis management missions and operations²⁰ and he was equally well aware that the European Union avoided to implement article 43.1 from the Treaty on European Union and

launch combat force operations for crisis management²¹. The French president was also at odds with the broad PESCO membership²² and its focus on capability building, given that he considered that PESCO had to bring together only states with a clear desire and capacity to deepen their defence cooperation and that it needed to give weight to the operational dimension²³. The interest of the French president for a defence initiative, parallel to CSDP, also reflected the importance he attached to the participation in the defence of Europe of both the United Kingdom, once Brexit was completed²⁴, and Denmark, which at that time had an opt-out from CSDP²⁵; the presence of the United Kingdom was considered essential on grounds of the Franco-British close defence cooperation in the framework of the Lancaster House Treaties (2010) which, among others, enabled the establishment of the Combined Joint Expeditionary Force (CJEF)²⁶. EI2 could also be regarded as an attempt by Macron to supplement in a broader context, the deep defence partnership of France with both Germany and the United Kingdom²⁷.

In less than a year, on June 23, 2018, following a formal invitation extended by France to selected countries, nine European states (Belgium, Denmark, Estonia, France, Germany, the Netherlands, Portugal, Spain, United Kingdom²⁸) signed, at the level of defence ministers, a Letter of Intent²⁹. The document defined EI2 as a "flexible, non-binding forum of European participating states"³⁰ designed to provide protection for the security interests of Europe, by means of fostering a strategic culture as a significant contributing factor to the conducting of military missions and operations, along the whole spectrum of crisis. The strategic culture was intended to be developed along four primary areas of cooperation, namely strategic foresight and intelligence sharing, scenario development and planning, support to operations and lessons learned and doctrine. It was emphasised that EI2 did not create military obligations affecting national sovereignty and that the defence cooperation objectives pursued through it were designed as complementary to those aimed at within the framework of the United Nations, European Union and NATO. With respect to PESCO, it

was emphasised that EI2 was intended to advance as much as possible its objectives and projects. From an administrative point of view, the document provided for the establishment of a Permanent Secretariat staffed with French personnel and located in Paris; the absence of an institutional framework for EI2 was explained as a reflection of Macron's preference for efficiency over bureaucracy³¹.

For the functioning of the EI2 it was agreed that its members would convene regularly at different levels. At the military level, high-ranking officials from the General Staffs meet twice a year, within the framework of the Military European Strategic Talks, while at the political level, the reunions bring together the defence policy directors, at least once a year, and, at the highest level and every one year, the defence ministers³². The first meeting in defence ministers format took place on 7 November 2018, in France, and provided the opportunity for the then French defence minister, Florence Parly, to emphasise that EI2 came in addition to the already existing solutions for the defence of Europe and to indicate that it will be active in the areas of disaster relief, natural disasters, maritime safety, and large-scale operations³³. After the Russian Federation launched its aggression against Ukraine, the ministers of defence from EI2 members came together in December 2022 at Oslo, where the building of a common strategic culture took the form of exchange of views on the situation in Ukraine and of a discussion based on scenarios³⁴.

The EI2 membership grew over time with the signing of the Letter of Intent by Finland (2018), Norway (2019), Sweden (2019) and Italy (2019)³⁵, so that currently 13 states are part of this initiative.

The EI2 facilitated two military actions in which European states, including France, got involved in Sahel and in the Middle East, namely the Takuba Task Force and Operation Agénor respectively³⁶. It should be mentioned that there are experts who do not link EI2 with these actions considering that they were mere ad-hoc military coalitions and therefore did not share with EI2 the objective of supporting in the long run the defence integration among European states³⁷.

With respect to the Takuba Task Force, when it was launched on 27 March 2020, the participants were two African states (Mali and Nigeria) and eleven European states which, except for the Czech Republic, were all E12 members (Germany, Belgium, United Kingdom, Denmark, Estonia, France, the Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Sweden)³⁸. Later on, the task force was joined by other E12 members (Italy, Finland) and by Hungary, Lithuania, and Romania³⁹. The task force, which operated under the chain of command of the preexisting French Operation Barkhane, reached the level of complete operational capacity on 2 April 2021, but, as a result of unfavourable political circumstances in Mali, came to a complete end in June 2022⁴⁰. Operation Agénor was the military dimension of the European Maritime Awareness in the Strait of Hormuz (EMASoH) which, following a strong backing from Paris, was established on 20 January 2020 by seven members of E12 (Belgium, Denmark, France, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Portugal) plus Greece. For over four years (25 February 2020 - 1 July 2024), Operation Agénor covered by means of naval and aerial forces the Persian Gulf, the Strait of Hormuz and part of the Arabian Sea⁴¹.

Common Security and Defence Policy and European Intervention Initiative: contiguity and incongruence

The development of a European strategic culture as the paramount objective assumed by E12 could be linked with the importance attributed by the *European Security Strategy* (2003) to the building-up of a common strategic culture within the EU. According to this document, strategic culture was required for the EU to effectively apply all means at its disposal in the field of crisis management and conflict prevention⁴². More recently, the *Strategic Compass for Security and Defence* (2022) emphasised the relevance for CSDP of a genuine common strategic culture developed on the basis of a common understanding of threats and challenges faced by the European Union⁴³.

CSDP represents, thus, the primary tool of the EU for creating a strategic culture among EU member states and, taking into account the participation in CSDP of some countries from outside the EU, also somehow broadly between European states⁴⁴. It is to be observed that, within CSDP, PESCO plays a central role in the endeavour of building a strategic culture among its participants⁴⁵.

Despite not being defined by the Letter of Intent establishing E12, strategic culture was taken by Florence Parly, the French minister of Defence, back in 2018, to mean that "European armed forces must know and understand each other, and be able to act quickly and effectively together"⁴⁶. On grounds of a more detailed meaning of strategic culture, which fits the overall concept referred to by Parly⁴⁷, it was argued that the founding members of the E12 did not share the same strategic culture⁴⁸; in the peculiar case of Germany, its reserved attitude towards involving its armed forces in interventions abroad, sharply contrasted with France's keenness to do it, an incongruity that was highly relevant, given the prominent role that the Franco-German defence cooperation played for the European security⁴⁹.

The feasibility of the E12 objective to develop a consistent strategic culture among European states raised doubts on grounds that such a culture did not emerge within the framework of much more complex Euro-Atlantic structures such as NATO, European Political Cooperation, Common Foreign and Security Policy and CSDP. This persistent failure is usually explained in geopolitical terms, namely by pointing out that the threat perception of states is heavily dependent on their vicinities⁵⁰.

Moving to the operational field, it is to be observed that, in 2021, conclusions of the Council of the European Union and the *European Union's Integrated Strategy in the Sahel*, commended the Takuba Task Force. It is also significant that the possibility of turning the Takuba Task Force into a CSDP operation found support among EU military officials, who appreciated that it would adequately complement the European Union Training Mission in Mali (EUTM)⁵¹. Aiming to broaden the European participation in the Takuba Task Force, France was supportive of strengthening links

with the EU and did not reject the prospect of including the task force under the scope of CSDP⁵². As for Operation Agénor, close cooperation between it and European Union Naval Force Operation Atalanta (EUNAVFOR Atalanta) gradually developed and led the European External Action Service to consider the integration of the former within the latter one⁵³. The potential merger of the two operations was welcomed by France, which, like in the case of the Takuba Task Force, was pursuing an increase of the number of contributing European states.

The preoccupation for connecting CSDP with Takuba Task Force and Operation Agénor was echoed in *The Strategic Compass for Security and Defence*, which set as one of the EU priorities in the area of CFSP, the development of close links with ad-hoc missions and operations under leadership of European states⁵⁴. To this purpose, the mentioned document indicated that there should exist reciprocal support between such ad-hoc missions and operations and CSDP missions and operations, when deployed in similar or close areas. Moreover, it was mentioned therein that ad-hoc missions and operations, led by European states, could receive support on the part of the European Union, if they further its interests.

Both operations facilitated by EI2, but especially the Takuba Task Force, prove the difficulty of aligning the EU approach to crisis management with the operations conducted against the background of EI2. With respect to Takuba Task Force, the mismatch resulted from it being considered as too close to the interests of France in the Sahel and as overfocused on military aspects of the crisis⁵⁵. The issue of French national interests underpinning Operation Agénor was also raised, in connection with incorporating it into EUNAVFOR Atalanta, but the abandonment of this project was mainly an outcome of the increased insecurity within the Red Sea, that determined the EU to launch, in 2024, the EUNAVFOR Operation Aspides⁵⁶.

As elements linking EI2 to PESCO, one could mention two PESCO projects: Co-basing⁵⁷ and Military Mobility. The first project was initiated in 2018, after the establishment of EI2 and had France as its coordinator. It

also brought together four other EI2 members (Belgium, Germany, Spain, the Netherlands) and the Czech Republic, which would latter join Takuba Task Force. The project, which lasted until 2023, aimed at improving how bases and support points from Europe and outside it were shared among participating states⁵⁸. As for the Military Mobility project, its contribution to bring EI2 closer to PESCO could lie in the fact that, since 2022, all EI2 participating states, that is including the United Kingdom and Denmark, are also part of this project⁵⁹.

Conclusions

EI2 and European Union share the objective of building a strategic culture so that, if EI2 succeeds in this endeavour, it seems that CSDP benefits out of this achievement because, the majority of EI2 members are also CSDP members. Moreover, it could be maintained that, when EI2 was launched, a strategic culture was yet to emerge through CSDP so that EI2 did not envisage to duplicate an already existing result, but to fill an obvious gap and thus to be instrumental in relation to CSDP. Put it briefly, EI2 would create faster and outside the EU framework what CSDP would produce slower and inside the EU. However, the strategic culture to be brought about by means of EI2 is most likely not the same as the one to which CSDP is designed to give raise to. First of all, the fact that the United Kingdom, a highly prominent actor in European defence, belongs to EI2, but left the EU, is liable to give a different shape to the strategic culture in the context of EI2, as compared to that within the CSDP framework. Additionally, the limited EI2 membership and the absence of any country from Central or Eastern Europe is expected to foster a strategic culture that evinces geopolitical peculiarities, which do not define the strategic culture that follows from the much wider and diverse EU membership. Taking into account that, in the context of the Russian aggression against Ukraine, the United Kingdom started to take part in CSDP and is likely to extend its involvement herein, and also that Denmark abolished its opt-out from CSDP, the similarity between CSDP and EI2 strategic cultures may be in-

creased. Finally, the centrality of France in EI2 is expected to make its interests more visible, within the strategic culture emerging out of this format of defence cooperation, as compared to the one associated with CSDP.

With respect to the operational dimension, the contemplated possibility of turning both Takuba Task Force and Operation Agénor into CSDP operations, indicates their relevancy for the EU and points towards a model of EU-EI2 interaction, where EI2 assumes the initiative and the EU comes in latter and takes it over. Under these conditions, EI2 and EU are not engaged in a competitive relationship, but complement each other. However, the operations facilitated by EI2 proved too close to the interests of France and thus difficult to accommodate with the broad approach advanced through CSDP. The same considerations are likely to affect the provision of support by the EU to operations facilitated by EI2. Consequently, EU-EI2 relationship in the operational field remains problematic, despite EI2 members being present in areas of concern for EU.

The differences separating EI2 from the EU are an expression of the incongruity existing between a narrow and a broad perspective on European defence issues and, therefore, between advancing European defence integration from outside or from within the EU. Consequently, for an effective complementarity to operate between EI2 and EU, the development of adequate solutions for broadening the outcomes of cooperation under EI2 should be considered.

Endnotes

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2, 2019 pp. 261-277, <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41295-019-00161-w>.

³ Yf Reykers, Pernille Rieker, *Ad hoc Coalitions in European Security and Defence: Symptoms of Short-term Pragmatism, no more?* p. 863, *Journal of European Integration*, vol. 46, no. 6, 2024, pp. 861-879, <https://doi.org/10.1080/07036337.2024.2349608>.

⁴ Diane Fromage, *Op. cit.*, p. 2.

⁵ United States, Canada, United Kingdom and Norway are involved in PESCO and EUNAVFOR Atalanta includes Colombia, South Korea and Montenegro. In November 2022, the United Kingdom joined the Military Mobility project run through PESCO and this marked its first participation in a EU programme since leaving the EU. Moreover, negotiations between the United Kingdom and the EU are currently underway for enabling the former to take part in CSDP missions and operations (See on these topics Elena Lazarou, Linda Tothova, *Third-country Participation in EU Defence*, European Parliament, European Parliamentary Research Service, 2022, [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/ATAG/2022/729348/EPRS_ATA\(2022\)729348_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/ATAG/2022/729348/EPRS_ATA(2022)729348_EN.pdf), 12. 08. 2024, Isabella Antinazzi, Simon Brawley, *UK-EU Relations and European Security* United Kingdom Parliament, The Parliamentary Office of Science and Technology (POST), 07 October 2024, <https://doi.org/10.58248/HS74>, 17. 07. 2024, European Union External Action Service, and *Permanent Structured Cooperation (PESCO) – factsheet*, p. 2, 22 March 2024, https://www.eeas.europa.eu/eeas/permanent-structured-cooperation-pesco-factsheet-0_en, 22. 08. 2024).

⁶ Yf Reykers, Pernille Rieker, *Op. cit.*, pp. 862-863 and Nico Groenendijk, *Flexibility and Differentiated Integration in European Defence Policy*, p. 109, *L'Europe en Formation*, vol. 2, no. 389, 2019, pp. 105-120, <https://doi.org/10.3917/eufor.389.0105> and Pernille Rieker, Mathilde T. E. Giske, *European Actorness in a Shifting Geopolitical Order: European Strategic Autonomy Through Differentiated Integration*, pp. 68, 83, Palgrave Macmillan, Cham, 2024.

⁷ Tuomas Iso-Markku, Tyyne Karjalainen, *Op. cit.*, p. 2, and Pernille Rieker, Mathilde T. E. Giske, *Op. cit.*, pp. 16-17. EI2 was characterised as a case of multi-speed or à la carte approach to European integration (See Tomasz Mlynarski, *The Implications of Strengthening European Strategic Autonomy' and Its Defence Capabilities for the Growth of France's Global Importance and Power*, p. 231, *Politeja*, no. 1(88/1), 2024, pp. 223-237, <https://doi.org/10.12797/Politeja.20.2024.88.1.13> and André Dumoulin, *L'initiative européenne d'intervention. Enjeux et supports*, p. 6, e-Note 25, Institut Royal Supérieur de Défense, 02 March 2018, <https://www.defence-institute.be/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/enote-25.pdf>, 14. 07. 2024).

⁸ Sandra Kröger, Thomas Loughran, *Op. cit.*, p. 704.

⁹ Tuomas Iso-Markku, Tyyne Karjalainen, *Op. cit.*, p. 6 and Sandra Kröger, Thomas Loughran, *Op. cit.*, pp. 704-706.

¹⁰ Christian Molling, Claudia Major, *Why joining France's European Intervention Initiative is the right decision for Germany*, *EGMONT – The Royal Institute for International Relations*, 15 June 2018, <https://www.egmontinstitute.be/why-joining-frances-european-inter>

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¹¹ Jean-Pierre Maulny, *L'initiative européenne d'intervention (IEI). Le désir d'une Europe plus autonome d'Emmanuel Macron*, p. 62, *L'Europe en Formation*, vol. 2, no. 389, 2019, pp. 51-66, <https://doi.org/10.3917/eu-for.389.0051>.

¹² Yf Reykers, *EU Battlegroups. From standby to standstill*, p. 50, standstill in John Karlsrud, Yf Reykers (eds.), *Multinational Rapid Response Mechanisms from Institutional Proliferation to Institutional Exploitation*, Routledge, London, 2019.

¹³ For the case of Sweden and Italy see Gunilla Herolf, Calle Håkansson, *The New European Security Architecture*, p. 8 and Nicole Koenig, *The European Intervention Initiative: A Look Behind the Scenes*, p. 3, Jacques Delors Institut, Berlin, 27.06.2018, https://www.hertie-school.org/fileadmin/user_upload/20180627_EII_Koenig.pdf, 27. 08. 2024.

¹⁴ Catherine Schneider, *La Coopération structurée permanente et l'initiative européenne d'intervention (IEI)*, p. 192, Paix et sécurité européenne et internationale, no. 11, 2019, pp.183-194, <https://shs.hal.science/halshs-03157503/file/Pse%2011.8.pdf>, 22. 08. 2024.

¹⁵ President of the French Republic, *Discours d'Emmanuel Macron pour une Europe souveraine, unie, démocratique*, Sorbonne, 26 September 2017, <https://www.elysee.fr/emmanuel-macron/2017/09/26/initiative-pour-l-europe-discours-d-emmanuel-macron-pour-une-europe-souveraine-unie-democratique>, 06. 07. 2024.

¹⁶ Tomasz Młynarski, *Op. cit.*, p. 224.

¹⁷ Jean-Pierre Maulny, *Op. cit.*, p. 60.

¹⁸ Christian Mölling, Claudia Major, *Op. cit.* and Dick Zandee, Kimberley Kruijver, *The European Intervention Initiative Developing a Shared Strategic Culture for European Defence*, p. 2, Netherlands Institute of International Relations Clingendael, Clingendael Report. September 2019, https://www.clingendael.org/sites/default/files/2019-09/The_European_Intervention_2019_17_08.2024.

¹⁹ Jean-Pierre Maulny, *Op. cit.*, pp. 60-61 and Niklas Nováky, *Op. cit.*, pp. 5-6 and Nicole Koenig, *Op. cit.*, p. 2.

²⁰ Christian Mölling, Claudia Major, *Op. cit.* and Claire Mills, *The European Intervention Initiative (EII/EI2)*, p. 1, United Kingdom Parliament, House of Commons Library, Briefing Paper no. 8432, updated 23 September 2019, <https://researchbriefings.files.parliament.uk/documents/CBP-8432/CBP-8432.pdf>, 31. 08. 2024. During the presidency of François Hollande, the EU was able to initiate the European Union Military Operation in the Central

African Republic (EUFOR RCA) in a three months' time and could not agree on providing it with a broad mandate (Niklas Nováky, *Op. cit.*, p. 6). See also Tomasz Młynarski, *Op. cit.*, p. 231, Nicole Koenig, *Op. cit.*, p. 4, and André Dumoulin, *Op. cit.*, p. 6.

²¹ Maxime Lefebvre, *Has the time come for European defence?* p. 7, Foundation Robert Schuman, The Research and Studies Centre on Europe, Schuman Paper no. 743, 02 April 2024, <https://www.robert-schuman.eu/en/european-issues/743-has-the-time-come-for-european-defence>, 18. 09. 2024. EU members were affected by what has been termed the "demand-side problem of European defence cooperation", namely their reluctance to recourse to force in crisis situations unfolding abroad (Niklas Nováky, *Op. cit.*, p. 1).

²² Germany successfully opposed the narrow approach to PESCO membership supported by France because it rejected the idea of turning PESCO into a strong incentive for differentiated defence integration within the EU. (See Niklas Nováky, *Op. cit.*, p. 6).

²³ Dick Zandee, Kimberley Kruijver, *Op. cit.*, p. 2, Niklas Nováky, *Op. cit.*, p. 6, Catherine Schneider, *Op. cit.*, p. 192, Tomasz Młynarski, *Op. cit.*, p. 230, and Nicole Koenig, *Op. cit.*, p. 2.

²⁴ Christian Mölling, Claudia Major, *Op. cit.*, Niklas Nováky, *Op. cit.*, p. 2, and Carlos Martí Sempere, *Military Capabilities*, p. 65 (note 12), in Diego López Garrido, Vicente Palacio, Rodrigo Castellanos (eds.), *A European Defence Union: Moving Forward. Report 2022*, Fundación Alternativas, <https://fundacionalternativas.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/La-defensa-europea-traduccion-DEF-digital.pdf>, 22.08.2024.

²⁵ Claire Mills, *Op. cit.*, p. 2.

²⁶ Jean-Pierre Maulny, *Op. cit.*, p. 62, Laurent Paccaud, *Initiative européenne d'intervention: vers l'avenir avec la facilité européenne de paix*, p. 108, *Revue Défense Nationale*, no. 813, October 2018, pp. 108-115, <https://doi.org/10.3917/rdna.813.0108> and Lorenzo Cladi, *Coping flexibly: role reorientation and the UK's military cooperation with European allies after Brexit*, *International Politics*, February 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41311-023-00428-w>.

²⁷ André Dumoulin, *Op. cit.*, p. 4.

²⁸ France invited these states on grounds of an analysis by its Ministry of Armed Forces of the French Republic, conducted while François Hollande held the office of the President of France, which indicated them as most capable to bring a relevant contribution to the defence of Europe (Alice Billon-Galland, Martin Quencez, *A Military Workshop*, 30 October 2018, <https://berlinpolicyjournal.com/a-military-workshop/>, 07. 07. 2024). Poland and Lithuania are said to have been interested in joining EI2 but did not receive such an invitation on the part of France (Niklas Nováky, *Op. cit.*, p. 10 and Nicole Koenig, *Op. cit.*, p. 3).

²⁹ Ministry of Armed Forces of the French Republic, *Letter of Intent between the Defence Ministers of Belgium, Denmark, Estonia, France, Germany, The Netherlands, Portugal, Spain and the United Kingdom Concerning the Development of the European Intervention Initiative (EI2)*, 25 June 2018, [MONITOR STRATEGIC](https://archives.defense.gouv.fr/con-</p></div><div data-bbox=)

tent/download/535740/9215739/file/LOI_IEI%2025%20JUN%202018.pdf, 22. 08. 2024.

³⁰ For its functioning as a forum, the EI2 was compared with European Political Cooperation in its early stages when it was not part of European Communities. (See Niklas Nováky, *Op. cit.*, p. 11).

³¹ Alice Billon-Galland, Martin Quencez, *Op. cit.*

³² Ministry of Armed Forces of the French Republic, *L'Initiative européenne d'intervention*, Ministry of Armed Forces, *Communiqué conjoint Initiative européenne d'intervention - Deuxième rencontre ministérielle défense de l'initiative*, 03 October 2019, <https://archives.defense.gouv.fr/dgris/action-internationale/l-iei/communiqué-conjoint-initiative-europeenne-d-intervention-deuxieme-rencontre-ministerielle-defense-de-l-initiative.html>, 13. 07. 2024 and Nicole Koenig, *PESCO and the EI2: Similar aims, different paths*. Policy Brief, Jacques Delors Institute, Berlin, 20 December 2018, PESCO and the EI2: Similar aims, different paths https://www.delorscentre.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/20181220_PESCO-EI2_Koenig.pdf, 18. 08. 2024.

³³ Permanent Representation of France to the European Union, *Défense européenne: première réunion ministérielle au format IEI*, 8 November 2018, <https://ue.delegfrance.org/defense-europeenne-premiere>, 01. 09. 2024 and Ministry of Armed Forces of the French Republic, *Défense européenne: première réunion ministérielle au format IEI*, 9 November 2018, <https://www.archives.defense.gouv.fr/actualites/articles/defense-europeenne-premiere-reunion-ministerielle-au-format-iei.html>, 12. 07. 2024.

³⁴ Government of Norway, *Joint Statement, EI2-meeting in Oslo*, 07 December 2022, <https://www.regjeringen.no/no/aktuelt/jointstatementei2/id2950118/>, 06. 08. 2024.

³⁵ Gunilla Herolf, Calle Håkansson, *Op. cit.*, p. 8 and Alexandra Brzozowski, *Macron's coalition of European militaries grows in force*, 24 September 2019, <https://www.euractiv.com/section/defence-and-security/news/macrons-coalition-of-european-militaries-grows-in-force/>, 19. 08. 2024.

³⁶ President of the French Republic, *Discours du Président de la République sur l'Europe à la Sorbonne*, Sorbonne, 24 April 2024, <https://www.elysee.fr/emmanuel-macron/2024/04/24/discours-sur-leurope>, 06. 07. 2024 and Ministry of Armed Forces of the French Republic, *L'Initiative européenne d'intervention a 3 ans: une défense européenne renforcée, efficace et réactive*, 22 June 2021, <https://archives.defense.gouv.fr/dgris/action-internationale/l-iei/l-initiative-europeenne-d-intervention.html>, 30. 08. 2024.

³⁷ Yf Reykers, Pernille Rieker, *Op. cit.*, p. 864.

³⁸ Prime Minister of the French Republic, Legal and administrative information department, *Déclaration politique des gouvernements allemand, belge, britannique, danois, estonien, français, malien, néerlandais, nigérien, norvégien, portugais, suédois et tchèque sur la Task Force Takuba au Sahel*, le 27 mars 2020, <https://www.vie-publique.fr/discours/274993-ministere-de-leurope-et-des-affaires-etrangeres-27032020-sahel>, 12. 07. 2024.

³⁹ Jean-Pierre Maulny, *Takuba Task Force: A New Approach to European Military Cooperation?* p. 5. Romania participated with 50 military personnel (Romanian Parlia-

ment, Decision no. 35 of June 16, 2021 on the participation of the Romanian Army, with forces, means and equipment, in the Task Force Takuba mission in the Sahel, under the leadership of France, starting with the fourth quarter of 2021, 16 June 2021, <https://legislatie.just.ro/Public/DetaliuDocument/243303>, 25. 07. 2024).

⁴⁰ Yf Reykers, Pernille Rieker, *Op. cit.*, pp. 868-869. The decision to begin the closure of the task force was taken at a high-level meeting held in Paris on 17 February 2022. (President of the French Republic, *Joint declaration on the fight against the terrorist threat and the support to peace and security in the Sahel and West Africa*, 17 February 2022, <https://www.elysee.fr/en/emmanuel-macron/2022/02/17/joint-declaration-on-the-fight-against-the-terrorist-threat>, 12. 07. 2024).

⁴¹ European Maritime Awareness in the Strait of Hormuz, <https://www.emasoh-agencor.org/>, 23. 07. 2024 and Ministry of Armed Forces of the French Republic, *EMASOH atteint sa pleine capacité opérationnelle le 25 février 2020*, 10 April 2020, <https://www.defense.gouv.fr/dgris/actualites/emasoh-atteint-sa-pleine-capacite-operationnelle-25-fevrier-2020>, 13. 07. 2024.

⁴² Council of the European Union, *European Security Strategy. A Secure Europe in a Better World*, p. 39, 2003, <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/30823/qc7809568enc.pdf>, 14. 08. 2024.

⁴³ Council of the European Union, *Strategic Compass for Security and Defence. For a European Union that protects its citizens, values and interests and contributes to international peace and security*, pp. 15, 17, 2022, https://www.eeas.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/strategic-compass_en3_web.pdf, 23. 07. 2024.

⁴⁴ Oliver Krentz, *Common Security and Defence Policy*, p. 1, European Parliament, Fact Sheets on the European Union, April 2024, https://www.europarl.europa.eu/erplapp-public/factsheets/pdf/en/FTU_5.1.2.pdf, 12.09. 2024.

⁴⁵ Nicole Koenig, *PESCO and the EI2: Similar aims, different paths*, p. 2, Jacques Delors Institute, Berlin, Policy Brief, 20 December 2018, PESCO and the EI2: Similar aims, different paths https://www.delorscentre.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/20181220_PESCO-EI2_Koenig.pdf, 06. 08. 2024, Permanent Structured Cooperation (PESCO), *Fostering a culture of collaboration: PESCO projects are ambitious, inclusive*, <https://www.pesco.europa.eu/pressmedia/fostering-a-culture-of-collaboration-pesco-projects-are-ambitious-inclusive/>, 07. 08. 2024, and Elena Lazarou, Tania Latici, *PESCO: Ahead of the strategic review*, pp. 1, 8, European Parliament, European Parliamentary Research Service, September 2020, [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2020/652051/EPRS_BRI\(2020\)652051_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2020/652051/EPRS_BRI(2020)652051_EN.pdf), 12. 08. 2024.

⁴⁶ Permanent Representation of France to the European Union, *Communiqué de presse du ministère des Armées: Huit pays rejoignent la France dans l'Initiative européenne d'intervention au service de la défense de l'Europe (25 juin 2018)*, <https://ue.delegfrance.org/huit-etats-membres-rejoignent-la#Communiqué-de-presse-du-ministere-des-Armees-Huit-pays-rejoignent-la-nbsp>, 11. 07. 2024. In the same vein, the French Ministry of Armed Forces latter defined strategic culture as "a shared perception of threats and helps breed solidarity within a

political community” (European Union Institute for Security Studies (EUISS), Direction générale des relations internationales et de la stratégie (DGRIS), *Strategic Culture: an elusive but necessary foundation for EU security and defence?* p. 1, June 2021, <https://www.iss.europa.eu/sites/default/files/EUISSFiles/Final%20Report%20-%20Strategic%20Culture.pdf>, 06. 07. 2024).

⁴⁷ The strategic culture could be specified as encompassing three levels that are interlinked, namely political-strategic, doctrinal and military-behavioural. The political-strategic level is made up of three elements: the aims whose attainment justify the use of force, the perception of threats, and the decision-making process; threat perception finds its expression in both the aims that could be reached by means of force and the national strategies in the fields of security and defence that are elaborated and approved according to the stages of decision-making peculiar to each country. The doctrinal level refers to how coercive means are to be employed, while the last level covers the national historical background of resorting to force. (See Dick Zandee, Kimberley Kruijver, *Op. cit.*, p. 7). For the breath of the concept of strategic culture, which captures the meaning attributed to it by officials of the French Ministry of Armed Forces but also by Dick Zandee and Kimberley Kruijver see the definitions by Jack Snyder, Ken Booth, Colin Gray, Alastair Iain Johnston, Robert Cassidy, Stephen Peter Rosen, John Duffield, and Jeannie Johnson, Kerry Kartchner Jeffrey Larsen (See Kerry M. Kartchner, *Defining and Scoping Strategic Culture. Promises, Challenges, and Conundrums*, p. 6 in Kerry M. Kartchner, Briana D. Bowen, Jeannie L. Johnson (eds.), *Routledge Handbook of Strategic Culture*, Routledge, London, 2024).

⁴⁸ Dick Zandee, Kimberley Kruijver, *Op. cit.*, p. 23.

⁴⁹ André Dumoulin, *Op. cit.*, pp. 5-6.

⁵⁰ Niklas Nováky, *Op. cit.*, p. 16.

⁵¹ Yf Reykers, Pernille Rieker, *Op. cit.*, pp. 868-869.

⁵² *Ibidem*, pp. 868-869.

⁵³ *Ibidem*, pp. 872 – 873.

⁵⁴ Council of the European Union, *Strategic Compass for Security and Defence. For a European Union that protects its citizens, values and interests and contributes to international peace and security*, pp. 11, 26.

⁵⁵ Yf Reykers, Pernille Rieker, *Op. cit.*, p. 870.

⁵⁶ *Ibidem*, p. 873 and Malin Karlsson, *A Preliminary Analysis of Naval Operations in the Red Sea: Aspides and Operation Prosperity Guardian*, Swedish Defence Research Agency, April 2024, <https://www.foi.se/rest-api/report/FOI%20Memo%208486,02.07.2024>.

⁵⁷ Dick Zandee, Kimberley Kruijver, *Op. cit.*, p. 5 and Nicole Koenig, *PESCO and the E12: Similar aims, different paths*, p.6, Policy Brief, Jacques Delors Institute, Berlin, 20 December 2018, PESCO and the E12: Similar aims, different paths https://www.delorscentre.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/20181220_PESCO-E12_Koenig.pdf, 12. 08. 2024.

⁵⁸ For the establishment and the conclusion of the Co-basing project see Council of the European Union, *Council Decision (CFSP) 2018/1797 of 19 November 2018 amending and updating Decision (CFSP) 2018/340 establishing the list of projects to be developed under PESCO*, article 1, Official Journal of the European Union, 21. 11.2018, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dec/2018/1797/oj>, 13. 08. 2024 and, respectively, Council of the European Union, *Council Decision (CFSP) 2023/995 of 22 May 2023 amending and updating Decision (CFSP) 2018/340 establishing the list of projects to be developed under PESCO*, point 12, Official Journal of the European Union, 23. 05. 2023, <https://www.pesco.europa.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/2023-05-22-Council-Decision-PESCO-projects-update-5th-wave-2023.pdf>, 13. 08. 2024. On the objectives followed through the Co-basing project see Permanent Structured Cooperation (PESCO), *PESCO Projects, [Closed] Co-Basing*, <https://www.pesco.europa.eu/project/co-basing/>, 11. 07. 2024.

⁵⁹ European Union External Action Service, *PESCO Projects. Military Mobility (MM)*, <https://www.pesco.europa.eu/project/military-mobility/>, 08. 07. 2024.